

THICK-WALLED “CRACK-FREE” CFRP PIPES USING NOVEL STRESS REDUCTION METHOD

Kazunori Takagaki¹ and Shu Minakuchi¹

¹Department of Advanced Energy, Graduate School of Frontier Sciences, The University of Tokyo
Mailbox 311, Transdisciplinary Sciences Building, 5-1-5, Kashiwanoha,
Kashiwa-shi, Chiba 277-8561, Japan

Email: takagaki@smart.k.u-tokyo.ac.jp (corresponding), web page: <http://www.smart.k.u-tokyo.ac.jp>

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) pipes are widely utilized for support structure of satellites due to its high stiffness and low thermal expansion, improving observation performance. Recently, the thickness and stiffness of the components have been increased with increasing size of observation equipments. Significant radial tensile stress, however, is induced in thick walled CFRP pipes during fabrication, leading to delamination in the worst case. Thus, this study aims to establish a stress reduction method for CFRP pipes, and to demonstrate a “crack-free” thick-walled CFRP pipe. First, theoretical and numerical analyses were addressed to investigate the effect of stacking sequence on residual stress. The result suggested that radial stress can be reduced by gathering circumferentially-stiff 90° layers as close to the inner surface as possible. Then, two pipe specimens were fabricated: one had a symmetric layup and the other had an asymmetric layup. Our fiber-optic-based monitoring system was utilized to capture internal strain development during curing. Higher non-axisymmetric strain was induced in the asymmetric layup, confirming the validity of the proposed method. Finally, a thick-walled CFRP was manufactured using the proposed method. No damage was observed in the specimen, achieving a crack-free CFRP pipe. Moreover, the specimen was cooled down to evaluate the full potential. It had 140 °C lower operation temperature than the conventional symmetric pipe. Additionally, a scheme for obtaining the optimized layup is briefly explained.

1 INTRODUCTION

Pitch-based carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) pipes are key structural elements for support structure of observation satellites. Their high stiffness and low thermal expansion improve the stability of the optical mirror, achieving high observation performance. Fig. 1 (a) illustrates a schematic of the optical instrument and support structure of SOLAR-B, a solar physics satellite built by Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) [1]. Recently, the thickness and stiffness of those support structure have been increasing due to the increasing size of optical instruments. Fig. 1 (b) shows an image of thick walled CFRP pipe. In thick-walled CFRP pipes, however, significant radial tensile stress is generated during curing, resulting in delamination failure in the worst case [2,3]. Fig. 2 (a) illustrates numerically calculated radial stress distribution in a thick-walled CFRP pipe after curing. The maximum stress arises near the through-thickness center, and delamination truly occurred at that point in a preliminary test (Fig. 2 (b)) [4].

So far, several studies have been conducted on CFRP pipes both numerically and experimentally. Sekine and Shin [5] investigated several factors related to cross-ply pipes using an analytic model based on quasi-static thermelasticity. They found that process induced residual stress can be reduced by controlling ply thickness and applying axial pre-tension during fabrication. Wisnom et al. [2,3] modeled chemical cure process and investigated the effect of three dimensional constraints arising from the mandrel (tool). The analysis and the accompanying experiment revealed that a heated mandrel suppress residual stress. A smart cure cycle was developed by Kim et al. [6]. The cycle adds rapid cooling and reheating to a conventional cure cycle. Radial-cut test was conducted and it was shown that the cycle reduced residual stress by 30%. Other researchers have developed non-destructive residual stress/strain measurement methods using optical fibers [7].

In spite of these efforts, the effect of stacking sequence has not been fully clarified. Furthermore, no studies have been conducted to fabricate thick-walled “crack-free” CFRP pipes, which are crucial elements for future high-precision satellites. This study develops a stress reduction method, and demonstrates a thick-walled crack-free CFRP pipe using the method. We began by examining the effect of stacking sequence on residual stress. Although symmetric layups are usually used for flat plates to achieve non-distorted shape, various layups can be applied for cylinders due to its axial symmetry. A simple theoretical analysis and finite element analysis (FEA) is conducted. The results propose a stress reduction method using asymmetric layup, which is quite different from the conventional symmetric layup. Then, an asymmetric pipe is fabricated along with a symmetric one to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method. Optical fiber sensors are embedded during fabrication, and radial strain development is monitored through curing using our monitoring system [4,8]. Finally, a thick-walled CFRP pipe is fabricated using the stress reduction method to demonstrate a crack-free CFRP pipe. Optic-fiber-based monitoring and cross sectional observation are conducted. Low temperature test is also conducted to the crack-free pipe to examine its full potential in severe condition. Moreover, a scheme for obtaining the optimized layup is briefly introduced to further improve the method. It is worth to note that the stacking sequences of support structures largely depend on the requirement of each mission. Thus, this research focuses on the most fundamental stacking sequence, cross-ply, to obtain a general insight into stress reduction. Additionally, we address only the cooling phase; the chemical cure reaction is neglected in this research because residual stress would be induced mainly due to thermal shrinkage after vitrification where stiffness significantly increases.

2 STRESS REDUCTION METHOD USING ATYPICAL LAYUP

We began by estimating the effect of layup on thermal residual stress using a simple theoretical approach. Then, FEA was conducted to further investigate the effect, and a stress reduction method was proposed based on these results.

Figure 1: Schematic of support structure in satellite, and (b) Image of a thick-walled CFRP pipe.

Figure 2: (a) Numerically calculated radial stress distribution, (b) Delamination failure in CFRP pipe.

2.1 Theoretical approach

Theoretical analysis was conducted to establish basic idea for stress reduction. Though previous work has rigorously formulated residual stress in CFRP pipes [5], a simple approach was used in this research to focus on the main cause of residual stress. Two dimensional plane strain state is assumed in the following.

The equation of equilibrium in the radial direction in a cylindrical system is given by

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} = 0, \quad (1)$$

where σ is the normal stress, r is the radial direction, and θ is the hoop direction. Integrating this equation leads to radial stress as

$$\sigma_r(r) = \frac{1}{r} \int_{r_0}^r \sigma_\theta(\tilde{r}) d\tilde{r} = \frac{1}{r_0/t + R} \int_0^R \sigma_\theta(\tilde{R}) d\tilde{R}, \quad (2)$$

where r_0 is the inner radius, t is the pipe thickness, and R is the normalized thickness defined by

$$R = \frac{r - r_0}{t}. \quad (3)$$

Eq. (2) implies that radial stress, σ_r , can be suppressed by reducing hoop stress, σ_θ .

Next, hoop stress is evaluated. We consider a cross-ply layup with the same number of 0° and 90° layers as an example. 0° is defined as parallel to the longitudinal direction of a pipe. Hoop stress in a pipe can be divided into two origins. One is the difference in thermal expansion between 0° and 90° layers. This stress is not affected by stacking sequence, and is easily calculated using rule of mixtures as

$$\sigma_\theta(r) = \frac{E_1 E_2 (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)}{E_1 + E_2} \Delta T = const, \quad (4)$$

where E is Young's modulus, α is the CTE, ΔT is the temperature change, subscript 1 denotes the fiber direction, and subscript 2 denotes the transverse direction.

The other origin of hoop stress is radial shrinkage. Radial shrinkage changes shape of an open curved specimen (Fig. 3 (a)), which is called "spring-in". In closed section like cylinders, however, its shape restrains the deformation, resulting in bending moment accompanying hoop stress (Fig. 3 (b)). The stress is evaluated in the following by calculating stress induced to correct spring-in (i.e., $\theta + \Delta\theta$) to original angle (i.e., θ). At first, radial deformation is estimated. Since carbon fibers prevented in-plane strain in both the longitudinal and hoop directions in a cross-ply layup, radial strain is given by

Figure 3: Schematic of (a) spring-in of open section and (b) residual stress in closed section.

$$\varepsilon_r(r) \cong \alpha_r (1 + \nu_{23}) \Delta T = \text{const}, \quad (5)$$

where α_r is the CTE in the radial direction, ν_{23} is the Poisson's ratio. Uniform strain is assumed for simplicity. Radial strain induces radial displacement, Δr , around the neutral axis, r_c . The radial displacement and the neutral axis are given by

$$\Delta r(r) = (r - r_c) \cdot \varepsilon_r, \quad (6)$$

$$r_c = \frac{\int_{r_0}^{r_0+c} E_{hoop}(r) \cdot r dr}{\int_{r_0}^{r_0+c} E_{hoop}(r) dr}, \quad (7)$$

where E_{hoop} is the Young's modulus in the hoop direction. This radial deformation generates hoop strain, ε_θ , and hoop stress, σ_θ , in a cylinder as explained above (Fig. 3 (b)). These values are estimated as

$$\varepsilon_\theta(r) = \frac{\Delta l}{l} = \frac{\Delta r(r) \cdot \theta}{r \cdot \theta} = \frac{(r - r_c) \cdot \varepsilon_r}{r}, \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_\theta(r) \cong E_{hoop}(r) \cdot \varepsilon_\theta(r) = E_{hoop}(r) \cdot \frac{(r - r_c) \cdot \varepsilon_r}{r} = E_{hoop}(r) \cdot \varepsilon_r \cdot \left(1 - \frac{r_c}{r}\right). \quad (9)$$

This hoop stress has different values with stacking sequences because it depends on the neutral axis, r_c . It is in contrast to the stress calculated in Eq. (4) which has the same value regardless of layups. Radial stress in Eq. (9) is induced mainly in 90° layers because of high Young's modulus in the hoop direction. Therefore, hoop stress can be suppressed by gathering 90° layers as close to the neutral axis as possible. As a result, radial stress is reduced since it is derived by integrating hoop stress (Eq. (2)).

2.2 Finite element analysis and stress reduction method

FEA was conducted using Abaqus 6.11 to assess the validity of the basic idea and to further investigate the effect of stacking sequence. A two dimensional model was used, and plane strain was assumed. In addition, a quarter part of a pipe was modeled for simplicity due to its axis symmetry. Boundary conditions constraining hoop movement was applied to reproduce whole cylindrical shape. The inner diameter and ply thickness was set to 15 mm and 0.125 mm, and material properties were based on a high modulus pitch-based graphite/epoxy (HYEJ15M65PD-25; Table 1). Four layups were investigated, with 24 plies in both the 0° and 90° layers: $[90_2/0_2]_{4S}$ (alternating symmetric model), $[0_{12}/90_{12}]_S$ (concentrated symmetric model), $[0_{24}/90_{24}]$ (outer 90° asymmetric model), and $[90_{24}/0_{24}]$ (outer 0° asymmetric model). They are illustrated in Fig. 4 with the boundary conditions. The two symmetric layups estimate the validity of the basic idea. The effect of the positions of 0° and 90° layers is evaluated by comparing the concentrated symmetric and two asymmetric layups.

Figure 4: Four stacking sequences investigated.

Fig. 5 shows radial stress distribution as a function of normalized thickness defined by Eq. (3). Radial stress is considerably suppressed in the concentrated symmetric layup compared with the alternating symmetric one, confirming the validity of the basic idea proposed in the previous section. In addition, low radial stress is generated in the two asymmetric models as well since the 90° layers are concentrated near the neutral axes. The lowest stress is induced in the outer 0° asymmetric model. It is attributed to the amount of spring-in induced when one constraint is eliminated (Fig. 6). Spring-in of the outer 0° asymmetric layup is suppressed because of thermal hoop shrinkage of the outer 0° layers. The reduced spring-in leads to small hoop stress, resulting in low radial stress (Eq. 2). In summary, radial stress in a CFRP pipe can be reduced by gathering the 90° layers close to the inner surface. Although cross-ply is taken as an example in this study, the proposed method can be applied to more practical layups which usually have several angles in addition to the 0° and 90°. According to the discussion above, stress can be suppressed by gathering circumferentially stiff layers close to the inner surface.

In the next section, CFRP pipes are fabricated to evaluate the stress reduction method using a fiber-optic-based monitoring system developed in our previous research [4,8].

	Elastic moduli (GPa)				Poisson's ratios		CTE ($\times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	
	E_{11}	E_{22}	G_{12}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	α_{11}	α_{22}
HYEJ15M65PD-25 (Unidirectional)	350	5.0	4.2	2.0	0.33	0.445	-0.3	40

Table 1 Material properties of HYEJ15M65PD-25.
(1 is fiber direction, 2 and 3 are transverse to fiber direction.)

Figure 5: Radial stress distribution as a function of normalized thickness.

Figure 6: Spring-in of two asymmetric layups and concentrated symmetric layup (Magnification: 15X).

3 EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

3.1 Radial strain measurement using FBG sensors

Optical fiber sensors are widely utilized for structural health monitoring (SHM). They have a lot of advantages: small diameter (150 μm), no necessity of electricity at sensing point, high sensitivity, and electromagnetic immunity. So far, they are used for axial strain monitoring and damage detection. Through-thickness strain measurement method, however, had not been developed even though it is a key technique for high reliability because composites have low through-thickness strength. Thus, we developed a through-thickness strain monitoring method using a fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor in previous works [4,8]. The method is utilized in this work, and it is briefly explained below.

Fig. 7 (a) illustrates a schematic of FBG sensor, which has periodic variation in the reflective index in the core. Incident light is propagated in the core area due to the total reflection. The coating is applied to reduce stress concentration around the cladding. When broadband light is illuminated into an FBG sensor, a narrow spectrum is reflected back at gratings (Fig. 7 (b)). The center wavelength of reflection spectrum, λ , is given by

$$\lambda = 2n\Lambda, \quad (10)$$

where n is the reflective index of core, and Λ is the grating period. The initial reflection spectrum has only one peak. Strain and temperature changes affect the reflective index and grating period, shifting the center wavelength. However, the spectrum splits into two peaks owing to the birefringence effect when the sensor is elliptically deformed in the cross sectional direction (Fig. 8). The difference between the center wavelengths, $\Delta\lambda$, of the two peaks, λ_p and λ_q , is expressed as

$$\Delta\lambda = |\lambda_p - \lambda_q| = n_0^2 (p_{12} - p_{11}) \lambda_0 \frac{|\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2|}{2}, \quad (11)$$

where n_0 is the initial refractive index of the optical fiber core, λ_0 is the center wavelength of the initial spectrum, p_{11} and p_{12} are the photoelastic constants, and ε_1 and ε_2 are the principal strains at the core in

Figure 7: (a) Schematic of FBG sensor, (b) Measurement principle of FBG sensor.

Figure 8: Reflection spectrum and cross sectional shape of FBG sensor. (a) Initial, (b) After cooling.

the cross sectional direction of the FBG sensor (Fig. 8). The constant in Eq. (11) is written as

$$k = n_0^2 (p_{12} - p_{11}). \quad (12)$$

The value was set to 0.42 by a preliminary test using several materials whose properties are known [4]. The Eq. (11) indicates that the difference $\Delta\lambda$ is proportional to the non-axisymmetric strain defined by

$$\varepsilon_d = \frac{|\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2|}{2}. \quad (13)$$

Thus, non-axisymmetric strain can be calculated using the difference $\Delta\lambda$. Non-axisymmetric strain indicates flattening of cross sectional shape of an optical fiber, and it is a good indicator of radial strain when the sensor is embedded near the neutral axis where in-plane strain, ε_2 , is negligible. The maximum radial stress is also induced near the neutral axis in a pipe. Thus, key strain development can be captured using FBG sensors embedded at that point. Note that strain transfer between host material and optical fiber is not perfect in the cross sectional direction; the strain measured by optical fibers are different from that of host materials. It is attributed to small diameter of optical fibers (i.e., less than 150 μm) and high stiffness of its material (i.e., fused silica glass: 73 GPa). However, measured strain properly indicates strain of host material because they are in proportion [9].

In our previous work [4], we embedded FBG sensors into a pipe and flat plate composites and measured non-axisymmetric strain development during curing. The difference of the sensor responses increased during cooling, successfully showing that the sensor captured radial strain induced in the pipe specimen. Numerical analysis was also conducted, and the result confirmed the validity of the method. This monitoring system is utilized in this research to capture strain development during fabrication of pipes, and to assess the validity of the proposed stress reduction method.

3.2 Methodology

Two 200 mm-long cross-ply pipes were fabricated to evaluate the validity of the proposed stress reduction method. One pipe had a conventional symmetric layup ([WF/90₂/0₆/90/0₃]_s), and the other had an asymmetric layup ([WF/90₃/0₂/90₃/0₁₆/WF]) based on the proposed method (Fig. 9). The same number of 0° and 90° layers was used for the two specimens (i.e., 18 plies of 0°, and 6 plies of 90°). A pitch-based high modulus prepreg sheet HYEJ15M65PD-25 (Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc.) was utilized for the 0° and 90° layers. Two 0° layers were introduced between 90° layers in the asymmetric layup to embed a FBG sensor in the 0° direction without disturbing the carbon fiber. WF stands for plain woven fabric layers (T300/#2500, Toray Industries, Inc., (45,-45)). In a preliminary test, transverse crack occurred in thick layers. The woven fabric layers were introduced on the pipe surface and/or within thick layers in this research to suppress these cracks. The surface fabric layers mitigate origins of surface crack, and the fabrics inside reduce the thickness of each continuous layer, which increases crack initiation strain [10]. Preliminary FEA confirmed that the woven fabric layers hardly affect residual stress because the stiffness in the 0° and 90° directions is relatively small due to the fibers with the 45° and -45° directions. In practical layup, where several angles are usually used besides 0° and 90° layers (i.e., 15°, 45°, 75° etc.), the same effect can be expected by placing these layers in the same way as the plain woven fabrics.

Figure 9: Two stacking sequences investigated and embedment points of FBG sensors

	Elastic moduli (GPa)				Poisson's ratios		Thermal expansion coefficients ($\times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	
	E_{11}	E_{22}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	α_{11}	α_{22}
Woven fabric layer ((45, -45) plain woven)	13.6	7.6	27.6	2.5	0.77	0.07	2.9	52
Cladding and core	73		-		0.16		0.25	
Polyimide coating	1.5		-		0.25		15	

Table 2 Material properties of (45, -45) plain woven fabric, optical fiber sensor, and coating material. (1 and 3 are in-plane direction, 2 is through-thickness direction)

When all the plies were cured at one time, tightly laid up prepregs became loose during vacuuming and compaction, resulting in large wrinkles with carbon fiber failure. Therefore, a few separated cure cycles were arranged for the specimens to prevent these wrinkles: three schedules (9, 7, and 10 plies) for the symmetric layup and two schedules (9, 17 plies) for the asymmetric layup. Prepreg sheets were laid up on an aluminum mandrel (30 mm diameter) coated with release agent. The mandrel was utilized only for the first cures, and prepregs were directly laminated onto the cured specimen and cured without mandrel after the second cure. The pipes were pressured by thermal shrinkage tubes, vacuum bagged, and cured in an autoclave under a gauge pressure of 0.3 MPa. The thermal shrinkage tubes slightly adhered on the specimen and became residue which causes unexpected delamination. Thus, the surface was lightly polished with 180-grit sandpapers before next curing to remove the residue. The polish would improve adhesiveness as well. The curing process was based on the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle, which consists of 2 °C/min temperature rise from room temperature to the curing temperature of 125 °C and holding for 2 hours. This cycle is common for both pitch-based prepreg and woven fabric prepreg.

An FBG sensor (Fujikura, Ltd., 150 μm diameter polyimide-coating, and 10 mm grating length) was embedded into each specimen during lamination. The sensor was aligned with the longitudinal direction of the pipes, and the grating area was placed at the longitudinal center of the pipes. They are embedded near the neutral axes of each pipe: between the 13th and 14th layer for the symmetric lay-up and between the 5th and 6th layer for the asymmetric lay-up (Fig. 9). Preliminary FEA showed that in-plane strain is negligible and radial stress is significant at the points. Thus, key radial strain development can be monitored using the FBG sensors, as discussed in the Section 3.1.

The FBG sensors were illuminated by an amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) light source (AQ2141, Ando Electric Co., Ltd.), and the reflection spectra were measured using an optical spectrum analyzer (AQ6317, Ando Electric Co., Ltd.). Internal temperature was also recorded using data logger (MV100, Yokogawa Electric Co., Ltd.) and K-type thermocouples embedded at the same interlaminar positions as the FBG sensors. The FBG response and temperature were measured through the curing processes at 1 min intervals with synchronization. Non-axisymmetric strain was calculated from the measured data using a Fortran program developed in the previous researches [4,8]. In addition, FEA was carried out to assess the validity of the experiment. The material properties of the fabric layer, optical fiber sensor and coating are listed in Table 2.

3.3 Results

Fig. 10 shows non-axisymmetric strain development during the fabrication as a function of temperature. FEA results are also plotted in the figure. 0 $\mu\epsilon$ is set to the strain at the onset of cooling to evaluate residual strain development during cooling. The experiment data increases almost linearly with decreased temperature, which slightly differs from the numerical data in the symmetric one especially for low temperature area below 50 °C. It would be attributed to two dimensional assumption and the lack of non-linear material properties in the analysis. Nevertheless, the experiment agreed well with the numerical analysis, confirming the validity of the tests.

In general composites, reinforce fibers constrain in-plane strain, inducing significant through-thickness strain during curing. Since this strain is contraction, it deforms the cross sectional shape of an optical fiber into horizontally long elliptical shape (Fig. 10). Consequently, non-axisymmetric strain

Figure 10: Non-axisymmetric strain development as a function of temperature.

is induced. Through-thickness tensile stress in a pipe reduces this deformation, leading to lower non-axisymmetric strain. Fig. 10 shows that non-axisymmetric strain in the asymmetric pipe exceeds that in the symmetric one. It indicates that radial tensile stress was reduced in the asymmetric pipe compared with the symmetric one, successfully confirming the validity of the proposed method.

4 FABRICATION OF THICK-WALLED CFRP PIPE

4.1 Methodology

A 200 mm-long thick-walled CFRP pipe was fabricated based on the stress reduction method to demonstrate a “crack-free” CFRP pipe. It was revealed in our previous research [4] that delamination failure occurs when a thick-walled CFRP pipe is manufactured with a conventional symmetric layup (i.e., $[0_2/90_2]_{6S}$: 48-ply). We used the same number of 0° and 90° plies as the previous research (i.e., 24 plies in both directions) in this test to fabricate the asymmetric CFRP pipe. The stacking sequence was set to $[[WF/90_8]_3/WF/[0_8/WF]_3]$ (55 plies). The same materials as described in the previous section were utilized. Separate cure schedules were set for the 55-ply specimen similarly to the fabrication described in the Section 3: the fabrication was separated into six (8, 8, 8, 8, 12 and 11 plies) separate cures. An FBG sensor was embedded during lamination. The sensor was placed between the 29th and the 30th ply, where both adjacent layers have fibers aligned with the longitudinal direction. The FBG cannot be used to monitor radial strain development because the embedment position is far from the neutral axis, and therefore the effect of circumferential strain would not be negligible. Our previous work [4], however, confirmed that delamination can be detected from discrete strain change since damage affects strain distribution in materials. Thus, the sensor was utilized as a damage detection device in this test. Temperature was also measured using K-type thermocouple embedded at the same interlaminar positions as the FBG sensor. The reflection spectrum and temperature was recorded at 1 min intervals with synchronization. Moreover, cross-sectional observation was conducted after fabrication using a microscope (VHX-2000, Keyence Co, Ltd.) to further confirm the quality of the asymmetric pipe.

In addition, low temperature test was conducted to the specimen after fabrication in order to evaluate the full potential of the crack-free pipe. The specimen was cut to 10 mm-long pieces, and three pieces near the longitudinal center were cooled from room temperature (20 °C) down to -180 °C using liquid nitrogen (LN_2). The test was interrupted every 20 °C and cross section was observed. The FBG sensor response was not measured because the sensor had been cut to observe the cross section.

4.2 Results

Fig. 11 shows non-axisymmetric strain development as a function of temperature. The figure also illustrates the result of the symmetric pipe manufactured in the previous test [4]. All the data continuously changes in the asymmetric layup except near 100 °C although discontinuous change is captured in the symmetric layup near room temperature (i.e., 20 °C) likely due to delamination failure. The discrete change near 100 °C would be attributed mainly to calculation error of the Fortran program, and raw spectrum data shifted continuously. This result indicates that no damage was captured in the

asymmetric pipe. Fig. 12 depicts cross sectional images of the (a) symmetric and (b) asymmetric pipes. Delamination failure is observed in the symmetric one, which would induce the discontinuous change in non-axisymmetric strain in Fig. 11. On the other hand, neither delamination nor transverse crack is seen in the asymmetric pipe, confirming the validity of the strain measurement and successfully demonstrating a crack-free thick-walled CFRP pipe. Note that the asymmetric pipe was fabricated without failure though the symmetric pipe was damaged during the separate cure schedules (i.e., only 39 plies were cured though 48-ply specimen was scheduled.).

Three 10 mm-long pieces were cut and cooled down to $-180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ after the fabrication. Fig. 13 (a) illustrates cross sectional view after $-180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Fig. 13 (b) is an enlarged view of red squared area in Fig. 13 (a). Delamination and transverse crack are observed in Fig. 13. Delamination occurred after $-160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in two pieces and $-120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in one piece. Meanwhile, crack was captured after $-160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in one piece and $-120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in two pieces. Though the strength varies likely due to quality variation after curing, the asymmetric pipe had more than $140\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ lower operation temperature than the symmetric one which broke at about $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. It is revealed from the results that the asymmetric layup method significantly improves the stability of structures even in a severe environment.

4.3 A scheme for optimized layup

Finally, a scheme for obtaining the optimized layup is briefly explained. The proposed stress reduction method gives a general idea. Although the method can be applied to practical use, it would be more beneficial if optimization is conducted by considering all the possible layups. Since FEA takes a lot of time, an theoretical model developed by Sekine and Shin [5] was applied for the optimization. The model assumes generalized plane strain, and the strain and stress are calculated by solving a system of linear equations with $2n+2$ variables which is led by boundary conditions. Here, n is the number of plies. The detail about the formulation is shown in the previous work [5].

A Python program was developed based on the theoretical model and the optimized layup was determined for a pipe with 10 plies in both 0° and 90° layers (i.e., total ply number is 20) as an example. Fig. 14 (a) illustrates the flow chart of the calculation. The material properties are pitch based graphite prepreg shown in Table 1. Inner diameter and the ply thickness are set to 15 mm and 0.25 mm. Fig. 14 (b) shows stacking sequences and corresponding maximum radial stress calculated.

Figure 11: Non-axisymmetric strain development in asymmetric and previously made symmetric pipe.

Figure 12: Cross sectional view of (a) symmetric and (b) asymmetric pipes.

Figure 13: Cross section of asymmetric pipe after cooling test. (b) Enlarged view of square area in (a).

White and dark boxes indicate 0° and 90° layers, and red line shows the place where the maximum stress is induced. Surprisingly, the optimized layup is the same as that proposed in the section 2, supporting the stress reduction method.

However, it should be noted that this optimization focuses only on radial stress. Transverse crack easily occurs in thick layers as described in the section 3.2. This effect will be introduced into the program in the future work by considering energy release rate by occurrence of the crack [10]. Moreover, calculation cost is enormous if all the possible layups are evaluated. The number of combinations calculated in this research is $C(20,10) = 184,756$, and it took about 2 hours to calculate all the layups using a personal computer. The number of combinations dramatically increases with the number of plies. Thus, the future work includes introducing mathematical optimization into the program. By resolving these issues, more sophisticated layup would be obtained.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This research aimed to develop a stress reduction method to achieve crack-free thick-walled CFRP pipes. We began by addressing the effect of stacking sequence on residual radial stress. Theoretical and numerical analyses were conducted, and they proposed a stress reduction method which uses asymmetric layup with gathering circumferentially stiff layers (e.g., 90° layers) close to the inner surface. Then two pipes were fabricated to evaluate the stress reduction method. One had a conventional symmetric layup and the other had an asymmetric layup based on the proposed method. FBG sensors were embedded into the specimens to monitor non-axisymmetric strain development during curing. The result showed higher non-axisymmetric strain in the asymmetric pipe than the symmetric one, confirming the validity of the proposed method. Finally, a thick walled CFRP pipe

Figure 14: (a) Flow chart of optimization, (b) Results for 20ply pipe with 10 0° and 10 90° layers.

was manufactured using an asymmetric layup. When the pipe is fabricated with a symmetric layup, delamination occurs during curing. However, no damage was observed in the asymmetric pipe, successfully demonstrating a “crack-free” thick-walled CFRP pipe. After the fabrication, the pipe was cooled down using LN₂ to assess the full potential of the pipe. It endured down to -120 °C, showing 140 °C lower operation temperature than the conventional symmetric pipe which broke at room temperature. Furthermore, a scheme for layup optimization was briefly explained.

However, several issues should be resolved for practical use. First, this study focused on only cooling phase, and chemical cure shrinkage was not considered. However, some studies suggested that damage may be induced by chemical cure shrinkage [2,3]. Thus, future work includes investigating its effect on residual stress. Even though, the proposed method would be applied because the fundamental mechanism is similar to each other. Second, the optimization process should be more sophisticated. Although a schematic of optimization process was proposed in this research, no damage criteria were introduced. Determining proper damage criteria is essential for optimization. By resolving these issues, the method will be more beneficial to designers and manufactures of CFRP pipes, which will result in significant performance improvement of future satellites.

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